

Deuterium Labelling Studies with Unsaturated Acids and Nitriles[†]

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α -Deuteriated α,β -unsaturated acids have been prepared by Knoevenagel condensation of aldehydes with deuteriated malonic acid. The decarboxylation of α,β -unsaturated cyano acid with pyridine/ D_2O yields α - and γ -labelled nitriles. The deuterium incorporation is studied by pmr spectroscopy.

DEUTERIATED compounds are useful for chemical as well as for biological work. α -Deuteriated enoic acids have been prepared earlier by deuterium exchange reaction under basic condition but the incorporation is poor¹. Manitto *et al.*² have reported the preparation of α -deuteriated cinnamic acids by Hofmann elimination of the quaternary ammonium salts in presence of deuterium oxide. In continuation with our work³ on the deuterium labelled acids, we report here a simple and efficient method for the preparation of α -deuteriated unsaturated acids by Knoevenagel condensation⁴ of suitable aldehydes with deuteriated malonic acid (prepared by exchange with D_2O). During this reaction in pyridine, decarboxylation of the substituted malonic acid occurs and the α -position is protonated. Since only deuterons are present in the reaction medium the resulting acid is α -deuteriated (Chart 1). The

R	%D
(1) <i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	68
(2) <i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	70
(3) <i>p</i> -OMeC ₆ H ₄	66
(4) <i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	65
(5) <i>p</i> -OH, <i>m</i> -OMeC ₆ H ₄	60*

* Keeping with piperidine and pyridine.

Chart 1

deuterium incorporation is determined by comparing the relative intensities of carefully determined integrals of the various signals. If 100% pure deuteriated malonic acid is used one should be able to get 100% α -deuteriated enoic acid by this method.

The decarboxylation of α,β -unsaturated malonic and cyano acids has been the subject of many

investigations. Corey^{5,6} and others⁷ have suggested isomerisation of the double bond to β,γ -position of the acid which then undergoes decarboxylation to yield β,γ - and α,β -unsaturated acids. We planned to use this for the multiple labelling of unsaturated nitriles. During the equilibration of the α,β - and β,γ -isomers of the cyano acid (6), the γ -position (methyl group) and the α -position can get labelled (Chart 2).

Chart 2

The decarboxylation of the cyano acid (6), prepared by Knoevenagel condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with acetophenone, and careful hydrolysis⁸ was carried out with pyridine in D_2O . The product was found to be a mixture of α,β - and β,γ -unsaturated nitriles which were separated by preparative tlc. The experiment was also performed in the absence of D_2O which yielded a mixture of undeuteriated nitriles, δ (CCl₄) 7.27 (s, Ar-H), 5.50 (m, olefinic-H), 3.43 (t, *J* 1.5 Hz, methylene-H), 2.43 (d, *J* 1.5 Hz, CH₃). Comparison of the methyl and methylene proton intensities gives the % of β,γ - and α,β -unsaturated nitriles as 83 and 17, respectively. The pmr of the deuteriated nitriles showed extensive labelling of α - as well as the γ -positions. Pmr of β,γ -unsaturated nitrile (7) δ (CCl₄, 60 MHz) 7.25 (100 mm, s, Ar-H), 5.47 (15 mm, d, *J* 5 Hz, partially

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labelled olefinic-H), 3.4 (6 mm, broad triplet, partially labelled methylene-H), clearly indicates that the γ position is labelled to the extent of 62.5% and the α -position 85%. Pmr of α,β -unsaturated nitrile (8) δ (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) 7.46 (193 mm, s, Ar-H), 5.64 (5 mm, bs, labelled olefinic-H), 2.46 (37 mm, broad multiplet indicative of coupling to D, labelled- CH_2). The integrated intensities indicate that the α -position is 87% labelled and the γ -position 68%. Since it is possible to convert β,γ -unsaturated nitrile into α,β -unsaturated nitrile, this represents an efficient method for α - and γ -labelling of α,β -unsaturated nitriles. The extensive labelling is explained in Chart 2.

Experimental

Typical procedure: Deuteriated malonic acid (0.5 g), anisaldehyde (0.5 g) and dry pyridine (4 drops) were heated on a water-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated acid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to yield pure α -deuteriated *p*-methoxycinnamic acid (0.570 g). The nmr integration of the signal at δ 6.35 (α -H) was compared with that at δ 7.62 (β -H and Ar-H) which indicated 66% deuterium at the α -position. The incorporation is not 100% since the deuteriated malonic acid used was only 69-70% deuteriated.

α,γ -Deuteriated- β -methylcinnamitrile (8): 2-Cyno-3-phenyl-2-butenic acid⁹ (6; 1.1 g), D_2O

(1 ml) and pyridine (10 ml) were refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether was distilled off to give a mixture of α,β - and β,γ -unsaturated nitriles (8 and 7, 0.79 g), which were separated by preparative tlc on silica gel. The compounds were characterised by comparison of spectral data with the known undeuteriated nitriles.

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